

Real-time Control of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles Using a Type-2 Fuzzy System

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Abstract: Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) are characterised by high-order nonlinear dynamics and uncertainties in terms of external disturbances and system parameters. Therefore, the control of these systems is very challenging. One of the effective approaches to alleviating this problem is to use type-2 fuzzy logic in control system design. The paper proposes a type-2 fuzzy controller (T2FC) for control of a quadrotor UAV. The configuration of the UAV system, along with its kinematic and dynamic-state-space models, is described. The two-level control structure based on T2FC is introduced for the quadrotor. The rule bases of the T2FCs are designed and implemented to control UAV's x , y , z positions, as well as its roll, pitch and yaw angles. Simulation results for the control of these positions and attitude angles are presented. The results obtained indicate the suitability of the proposed T2FC-based system for the real-time control of the UAV.

Keywords: Fuzzy control, UAV, Type-2 fuzzy controller, Rule base

1. INTRODUCTION

The movement of a UAV in three-dimensional space is accomplished through the coordinated control of roll, pitch, yaw angles and upward action. The control of these variables is performed by changing the rotational speeds of the UAV's motors [1,2]. In civil applications, UAVs, which are also known as quadrotors, are widely used for traffic monitoring, natural disaster assessment, fire detection and control, aerial photography for mapping, power line inspection, crop monitoring, atmospheric analysis of weather forecasting, inspection of imports and exports at the border, search-and-rescue operations, etc. UAVs are also extensively employed in military applications. However, their dynamics are highly nonlinear and extremely complex. Due to their complicated structural configuration and nonlinear behaviour, the control of UAVs is very challenging. Furthermore, external disturbances can rapidly affect their performance and compromise system stability. During a mission, a quadrotor UAV may encounter various sources of uncertainty [3,4]. These uncertainties may arise from variations in aerodynamic coefficients, control surface failures and unexpected external disturbances. Sometimes, large control gains are employed to rapidly reduce tracking errors, thereby achieving fast adaptation and compensating for these uncertainties. However, high adaptation gains may introduce high-frequency components into the control response, which can lead to poor transient behaviour. Therefore, the development of an effective control system for a UAV remains a challenging task. Different control architectures have been developed to improve the transient response of UAVs and to ensure stable operation under various flight conditions.

Some research papers have developed PID controllers [3,4] for UAV control. However, due to the complex and nonlinear nature of UAV dynamics, using a PID

controller for quadrotor control can limit system performance. In reference [5], a PID controller was employed for waypoint-tracking control of a UAV and suppression of the disturbance. Two PD- and two PI controllers were applied for tracking control. The paper [6] implemented integral backstepping control for altitude and attitude control, considering variations in aerodynamic coefficients arising from vehicle motion. In [7], a robust algorithm was applied for attitude tracking, achieving effective error minimization. The reference [8] employed an H_∞ controller for quadrotor control and the control system demonstrated high robustness. In [9], a state feedback approach was used to design the controller, and point-to-point control was applied to move the system from one stable point to another. The research [10] presented a control system using PID controller with feedback linearization. Numerous studies have also investigated adaptive control of UAVs, including backstepping control [11], double closed-loop with disturbance rejection control [12], an event triggered control [13], backstepping adaptive control schemes [14,15], an adaptive non-singular mode control [16], a finite-time fault-tolerant tracking control [17], double closed-loop control strategy [18], sliding mode control [19], NN based event-triggered control strategy using reinforcement learning [20], modified uncertainty and disturbance estimator [21], a nonlinear three-loop cascade controller [22], a hierarchical control algorithm [23], modified super twisting control [24], H_∞ control approach [25], and a steady-state linear quadratic regulator (LQR) [26]. To handle uncertainty and estimate unknown disturbances, the authors of [27, 28] proposed a multilayer neural dynamic model for UAVs. The convergence and robustness of the proposed system were analyzed. In [28], a self-tuning adaptive controller was incorporated into a multilayer neural dynamic model (MLDM) to handle parameter uncertainty. Using the presented neural dynamic control system, the UAV was

able to perform time-varying trajectory tracking. The model was employed to estimate unknown disturbances and address model uncertainties. In references [28-31], neural networks (NNs) were used to design controllers that enhance UAV control performance. These controllers were applied to position and attitude control, with NNs used to approximate external disturbances.

The research studies discussed above have shown good performance in UAV control. However, quadrotors UAV often fly in unknown environments and under uncertain conditions. Certain ill-defined and complex events, such as ground effect, airflow interactions and propeller flapping, have been investigated but are difficult to model due to their complexity. Moreover, UAVs' dynamics are highly nonlinear and subject to significant uncertainties in both rotational and translational motion. The controllers discussed above have shortcomings in dealing with ill-defined problems and uncertainties. Under these conditions, fuzzy control offers an alternative, as it is based on human expert knowledge. Fuzzy controllers can effectively handle nonlinear and uncertain systems and provide inherent robustness.

Recently, fuzzy rule-based controllers have been constructed to model uncertainties in the nonlinear dynamics of UAVs. References [32,33] designed fuzzy controllers for the control of UAV position and orientation. In [32], the fuzzy controller demonstrated superior performance compared with a classical PID controller. In [33], using sliding mode and backstepping approaches, a hybrid fuzzy controller was presented. The controller was able to remove the chattering effect. In [34], a robust flight control system was presented that employed two PD controllers together with a fuzzy terminal sliding mode controller. The proposed system stabilized the quadrotor and tracked a predefined trajectory despite external disturbances and model uncertainties. Mamdani if-then rules were employed to identify the quadrotor dynamics and external disturbances. Reference [35] presented a robust fuzzy controller based on a Linear Quadratic Regulator (LQR). The MFs representing the parameters of the controller were optimised using a high-exploration PSO algorithm. In [36], a fuzzy Pade controller was proposed based on fuzzy approximations and fuzzy singleton rules. In [37], quadrotor attitude control under external disturbances was implemented using a fuzzy model predictive controller. In this study, a fuzzy predictive control scheme was developed using a TS fuzzy rule base and a disturbance observer. In [38,39], fuzzy adaptive controllers were designed for UAV control. The authors of [39] utilised a fuzzy sliding mode approach for quadrotor control. In addition to the primary fuzzy system, a parallel fuzzy system was incorporated to enhance robustness and ensure system stability. The paper [40] presented a fuzzy adaptive fixed-time sliding mode controller for trajectory tracking. A fixed-time state observer was employed to estimate unmeasured states. The proposed system was applied to control a high-order nonlinear plant in the presence of external disturbances and uncertainties. The papers [41,42] designed fuzzy gain scheduling systems for the control of UAVs. In reference [42], an interval T2FS was

utilized to develop a backstepping controller for regulating the UAV's position.

Fuzzy logic systems are extensively used to control systems characterised by uncertainties and nonlinear dynamics. UAVs comprise multiple control variables that are interconnected within a unified dynamic structure. These variables exhibit complex nonlinear behaviour. To control each variable, individual subsystems are designed and integrated into a single control framework. However, handling uncertainties within each of these interconnected subsystems remains challenging. Uncertainties caused by changes in aerodynamic coefficients, control surface failures, and unexpected external disturbances complicate the control of UAVs. In such situations, an important approach is the use of type-2 fuzzy logic (T2FL). Type-2 fuzzy systems (T2FSs) can represent local nonlinearities of the dynamic plant and effectively manage uncertainties. T2FSs enable the representation of unknown components of UAV dynamic equations, thereby reducing the need for complex mathematical modelling. In T2FS, the premise and consequent components of the rules are represented as type-2 fuzzy sets. This provides greater flexibility in achieving the near-optimal performance of the control system. Due to the use of type-2 membership functions (MFs), T2FS can effectively handle inertial and external disturbances. Type-2 fuzzy sets was first proposed by L.A.Zadeh [43]. Later, J.M.Mendel [44] significantly advanced the theory of T2FS. T2FSs have been widely applied to solve different problems. These are time-series forecasting [45], dynamic plant identification and control [46,47], estimation of energy performance [48], and robotics [49,50].

Analysis of existing research studies indicates that UAVs exhibit high-order nonlinear dynamics and are subject to significant uncertainties in both rotational and translational motion. Variations in aerodynamic coefficients, control surface failures and unexpected external disturbances are major sources of these uncertainties. Under such conditions, the use of T2FL in controller design provides an effective approach to UAV control. The contributions of the paper include:

- A type-2 fuzzy rule-based control system is proposed for a UAV.
- A two-level control structure for a quadrotor UAV based on T2FS is proposed.
- Controllers for regulating UAV state variables are designed using a type 2 interval algorithm.
- Simulation studies are carried out to evaluate the transient response of the T2FC-based control system under various reference signals.

The paper includes seven sections. Section 2 describes the problem statement. Section 3 gives a brief overview of the kinematics and dynamics. Section 4 introduces the UAV control architecture based on T2FC. Section 5 presents the theoretical background of the proposed T2FC. Section 6 describes the results of the simulation. Section 7 presents the conclusions.

2. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

The UAV is controlled by four rotors mounted in orthogonal directions (Fig.1(a)). Two opposing rotors rotate clockwise, while the other pair rotates in a

counter-clockwise direction in order to balance the torque. The motors drive the propellers, which generate forces F_1, F_2, F_3 and F_4 . Rotors, numbered as 2 (left) and 4 (right), rotate clockwise, whereas rotors, numbered as 1 (front) and 3 (rear), rotate counterclockwise (see Fig.1(b)). The quadrotor tracks the target position by controlling the yaw, roll and pitch angles. By selecting the rotation speeds of the rotors, we can regulate these angles. By setting the angular velocities of all rotors equal, the quadrotor generates a net vertical lift force. The roll is controlled by regulating the relative speeds of the left and right propellers, while the pitch angle is controlled by regulating the relative speeds of the front and rear propellers. Yaw control is achieved by introducing a speed difference between the two counter-rotating rotor pairs (left-and-right and front-and-rear), producing a net torque about the vertical axis. The x, y and z positions are controlled through coordinated regulation of the ψ, ϕ and θ angles. Consequently, the main problem in UAV control is the precise regulation of the rotor angular velocities.

(a)

(b)

Fig.1. Configuration of UAV. (a) Quadrotor UAV, (b) Configuration

3. QUADROTOR UAV KINEMATICS AND DYNAMICS

In the paper, UAV dynamics are presented using both local and global coordinate systems. The local coordinate system, referred to as the body-fixed frame (BFF), is expressed by $\mathbf{B}=(x_b, y_b, z_b)$, while the global coordinate system, referred to as the earth-fixed frame (EFF), is denoted by $\mathbf{E}=(x, y, z)$. The centre of mass of the UAV is represented by point C, which defines the BFF's origin. The kinematic relations between the BFF and the EFF is

expressed by a transformation matrix (TM) from $\{x_b, y_b, z_b\}$ to $\{x, y, z\}$ as follows

$$\mathbf{R} = \begin{bmatrix} c\psi \cdot c\theta & c\psi \cdot s\theta \cdot s\phi - c\phi \cdot s\psi & c\psi \cdot c\phi \cdot s\theta + s\phi \cdot s\psi \\ c\theta \cdot s\phi & c\phi \cdot c\psi + s\psi \cdot s\phi \cdot s\theta & s\psi \cdot c\phi \cdot s\theta - c\psi \cdot s\phi \\ -s\theta & c\theta \cdot s\phi & c\phi \cdot c\theta \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where $c\phi=\cos(\phi)$, $c\theta=\cos(\theta)$, and $c\psi=\cos(\psi)$, while $s\theta=\sin(\theta)$, $s\phi=\sin(\phi)$ and $s\psi=\sin(\psi)$. The angles ψ, ϕ and θ represent the yaw, roll and pitch angles, respectively.

Let $\mathbf{v}_b = [\dot{x}_b \ \dot{y}_b \ \dot{z}_b]^T$ and $\mathbf{v} = [\dot{x} \ \dot{y} \ \dot{z}]^T$ be the absolute linear velocity vectors of the UAV expressed in the BFF and EFF, respectively. The relationship between them is given by $\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{R}\mathbf{v}_b$. The TM relating the angular rates from the BFF to those in the EFF is given by

$$\mathbf{T}(\phi, \theta, \psi) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & s\phi \ t\theta & c\phi \ t\theta \\ 0 & c\phi & -s\phi \\ 0 & \frac{s\phi}{c\theta} & \frac{c\phi}{c\theta} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where $t\theta=\tan(\theta)$. The attitude vector $\mathbf{o} = [\phi \ \psi \ \theta]^T$ is expressed by the three Euler's angles. The time derivatives of these parameters will define the angular velocity vector $\mathbf{w} = [\dot{\phi} \ \dot{\psi} \ \dot{\theta}]^T$ defined in EFF, while $\mathbf{w}_b = [p \ q \ r]$ represents angular velocity components in the BFF. The relationship between these vectors is given by $\mathbf{w} = \mathbf{T}\mathbf{w}_b$, that is

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{\phi} \\ \dot{\theta} \\ \dot{\psi} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & s\phi \ t\theta & c\phi \ t\theta \\ 0 & c\phi & -s\phi \\ 0 & \frac{s\phi}{c\theta} & \frac{c\phi}{c\theta} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} p \\ q \\ r \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} p & p + qs\phi \ t\theta + r c\phi \ t\theta \\ q c\phi - r s\phi \\ qs\phi/c\theta + rc\phi/c\theta \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

The UAV dynamics can be modelled using either the Newton-Euler formulation or the Newton-Lagrange approach [2]. The following assumptions are made to drive the dynamic model. Because the UAV uses electrical motors, its mass is assumed constant during flight. Also, compressibility and elasticity effects are neglected, and the UAV is modelled as a rigid body. Assume that, the thrust and aerodynamic drag produced by each rotor are proportional to the square of its angular speed, and each rotor is driven by an independent input. Accordingly, the total thrust applied to the UAV can be formulated as

$$F_i = b\delta_i^2 \quad (4)$$

Here, b is the thrust coefficient obtained from static thrust testing. δ_i ($i=1, \dots, 4$) is the angular speed of the i -th rotor.

Under the assumption that each propeller's torque is proportional to its thrust, the total thrust magnitude is $T = \sum_{i=1}^4 F_i$. The reaction torque produced by each rotor can be expressed as

$$\tau_i = (-1)^i c_{\tau} \frac{F}{\tau_i} \quad (5)$$

Where c_{τ} represents the propeller torque coefficient. In the BFF, the total thrust T and total moment vector τ are given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} T \\ \tau_\phi \\ \tau_\theta \\ \tau_\psi \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & F_1 \\ 0 & l & 0 & -l & F_2 \\ l & 0 & -l & 0 & F_3 \\ -c_\tau & c_\tau & -c_\tau & c_\tau & F_4 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} F_2 \\ F_3 \\ F_4 \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

where l denotes the distance from the rotor centers to the center of mass. c_τ is the positive constant,

The mathematical model of the UAV dynamics is developed using the following formulas [2,3, 36].

$$\ddot{x} = (\cos \phi \cdot \sin \theta \cdot \cos \psi + \sin \psi \cdot \sin \phi) \frac{u_1}{m} \quad (7)$$

$$\ddot{y} = (\sin \theta \cdot \sin \psi \cdot \cos \phi - \cos \psi \cdot \sin \phi) \frac{u_1}{m} \quad (8)$$

$$\ddot{z} = -g + (\cos \phi \cdot \cos \theta) \frac{u_1}{m} \quad (9)$$

$$\ddot{\phi} = \frac{(J_y - J_z)}{I_x} \dot{\theta} \dot{\psi} + \frac{J_r}{I_x} \dot{\theta} \dot{\delta} + \frac{l^m}{I_x} u \quad (10)$$

$$\ddot{\theta} = \frac{(J_x - J_z)}{I_y} \dot{\phi} \dot{\psi} - \frac{J_r}{I_y} \dot{\phi} \dot{\delta} + \frac{l^m}{I_y} u \quad (11)$$

$$\ddot{\psi} = \frac{(J_x - J_y)}{I_z} \dot{\theta} \dot{\phi} + \frac{l}{I_z} u_4 \quad (12)$$

Here ϕ , θ , and ψ denote the roll, pitch and yaw angles.; m is the mass of the UAV; l is the rotor arm's length from the origin point O (see Fig. 1(b)); ω is the rotor's angular velocity; J_r is the rotor's inertia; I_x, I_y, I_z are the mass moment of inertias;

The rotor's input signals u_1, u_2, u_3 and u_4 are equivalent to the $T, \tau_\phi, \tau_\theta, \tau_\psi$. Here, $u_2 = F_2 - F_4$; $u_1 = F_1 + F_2 + F_3 + F_4$; $u_4 = c_\tau(-F_1 + F_2 - F_3 + F_4)$; $u_3 = F_1 - F_3$; u_1, u_2, u_3 and u_4 are determined as

$$u_1 = b(\delta_1^2 + \delta_2^2 + \delta_3^2 + \delta_4^2) \quad (13)$$

$$u_2 = b(-\delta_2^2 + \delta_4^2) \quad (14)$$

$$u_3 = b(\delta_1^2 - \delta_3^2) \quad (15)$$

$$u_4 = d(-\delta_1^2 + \delta_2^2 - \delta_3^2 + \delta_4^2) \quad (16)$$

where δ_i ($i=1, \dots, 4$) are the angular velocities of the four rotors, and b and d are the thrust and drag coefficients, respectively [2].

4. TYPE-2 FUZZY CONTROL ARCHITECTURE OF UAV

As shown in the dynamic model (7)-(12), x, y, z, ϕ, θ and ψ are control variables. T2FCs are proposed to regulate the x, y , and z positions as well as yaw- ψ , roll- ϕ and pitch- θ angles. As is well known, PID controllers are widely used in industry for controlling dynamic systems, and their parameter selection typically relies on accurate plant models. However, when system dynamics are characterised by external disturbances, parameter uncertainties and strong nonlinearities, the application of PID controllers to UAV control becomes challenging.

Moreover, achieving reliable performance over long operating periods is very important. Under such conditions, conventional PID controllers may not adequately represent the system dynamics.

Fig.2 shows the type-2 fuzzy control system (T2FCS) structure for the UAV. The UAV has four control channels. These are z control channel, $x - \phi$ control channel, ψ control channel and $y - \theta$ control channel. Effective control of these dynamic channels requires generating the appropriate control signal. The altitude (z) and yaw (ψ) channels are directly controlled by T2FC, producing the control signals U_1 and U_4 , respectively (see Fig.2). Here, U_1 is computed from the T2FC output of z channel U_z , while U_4 is obtained from the T2FC designed for ψ channel. The $x - \phi$ and $y - \theta$ channels each employ two controllers to calculate the control signals U_2 and U_3 correspondingly. These output signals are used to regulate the x and y positions (coordinates) of the UAV.

Fig.2. T2FC-based control system.

Based on Newton's formula, the control forces along the z, x, and y directions are determined as

$$U_z = m\ddot{z}; \quad U_x = m\ddot{x}; \quad U_y = m\ddot{y} \quad (17)$$

Using Equations (7) and (8), we can determine the desired values of ϕ^d and θ^d .

$$\phi^d = \arcsin\left(\frac{m\ddot{x} \sin\psi - \frac{m\ddot{y}}{U_1} \cos\psi}{U_1 \frac{m\ddot{x} - \sin\phi \sin\psi}{\cos\phi \cos\psi}}\right) \quad (18)$$

$$\theta^d = \arcsin\left(\frac{U_1 \frac{m\ddot{x} - \sin\phi \sin\psi}{\cos\phi \cos\psi}}{\cos\phi \cos\psi}\right) \quad (19)$$

$$U_1 = \frac{(\ddot{z} + \dot{g})m}{\cos\theta \cos\phi} \quad (20)$$

Based on the current and desired values of ϕ and θ , the outputs of T2FCs for controlling the roll (ϕ) and pitch (θ) variables are determined.

Six controllers are designed for the UAV control (see Fig.2). In the control loop, the current plant output is compared with the set-point signal, generating a control error. Based on the current and previous error values, the change-in-error is calculated. Both the error and its change serve as inputs to the controllers. Based on these input signals, the T2FC computes the controller output, which is then applied to control the UAV.

The input-output relationships of these controllers can be expressed as $(e_z, \Delta e_z) \rightarrow U_z$, $(e_x, \Delta e_x) \rightarrow U_x$, $(e_y, \Delta e_y) \rightarrow U_y$, $(e_\psi, \Delta e_\psi) \rightarrow U_\psi$, $(e_\theta, \Delta e_\theta) \rightarrow U_\theta$, $(e_\phi, \Delta e_\phi) \rightarrow U_\phi$. T2FL is employed to construct these controllers.

5. TYPE-2 FUZZY CONTROLLER

The basic component of a T2FC is its knowledge base. For the UAV controllers, the knowledge bases are constructed based on the relationship between the input signals, error e and change-in-error e', and control signal U; that is, $(e_z, \Delta e_z) \rightarrow U_z$, $(e_x, \Delta e_x) \rightarrow U_x$, $(e_y, \Delta e_y) \rightarrow U_y$, $(e_\psi, \Delta e_\psi) \rightarrow U_\psi$, $(e_\theta, \Delta e_\theta) \rightarrow U_\theta$, $(e_\phi, \Delta e_\phi) \rightarrow U_\phi$. In this study, the relationships are implemented using Mamdani-type type-2 fuzzy rules. The IF-Then rule base consists of multi-input single-output rules, as presented below:

$$\text{If } x_1 \text{ is } A_{1j} \text{ and } x_2 \text{ is } A_{2j} \text{ and } \dots x_m \text{ is } A_{mj} \text{ Then } y \text{ is } B_j \quad (21)$$

where A_{ij} and B_j represent the type-2 fuzzy sets corresponding to the inputs and outputs, where $i=1, \dots, m$, $j=1, \dots, n$.

In the rule base, interval type-2 fuzzy sets are employed to express the values of the input-output variables (Fig.3). In this study, interval-valued triangular MFs are employed to describe these fuzzy sets. Each type-2 fuzzy MF is represented by a lower MF $\underline{\mu}_A(x)$ and an upper MF $\bar{\mu}_A(x)$.

$$\mu_{\sim i}(x_k) = [\mu_{\sim i}(x_k), \bar{\mu}_{\sim i}(x_k)] = [\underline{\mu}_i^k, \bar{\mu}_i^k] \quad (22)$$

The firing strengths of the rules are determined using the t-norm min operation. This operation is employed to compute the upper and lower membership grades of each active rule.

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{f} &= \underline{\mu}_{A_1}(x_1) * \underline{\mu}_{A_2}(x_2) * \dots * \underline{\mu}_{A_n}(x_n); \\ \bar{f} &= \bar{\mu}_{A_1}(x_1) * \bar{\mu}_{A_2}(x_2) * \dots * \bar{\mu}_{A_n}(x_n) \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

Fig. 3. Type-2 fuzzy membership function

where * denotes t-norm min operation. After the firing strengths are determined, type-reduction and defuzzifications are applied to compute the system output. For this purpose, the Karnik-Mendel algorithm [44,45] is employed to find the left and right endpoints.

$$y_l = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^M f_i y_i^l}{\sum_{i=1}^M f_i}; \quad y_r = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^M f_i y_i^r}{\sum_{i=1}^M f_i} \quad (24)$$

where $f^i \in F^i = [\underline{f}_i^i, \bar{f}_i^i]$, $y_i = [y_i^l, y_i^r]$. The output signal is determined as

$$\begin{aligned} y_l &= \frac{\sum_{i=1}^L f_i y_i^l + \sum_{i=L+1}^M f_i y_i^l}{\sum_{i=1}^L f_i + \sum_{i=L+1}^M f_i}; \quad y_r = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^R f_i y_i^r + \sum_{i=R+1}^M f_i y_i^r}{\sum_{i=1}^R f_i + \sum_{i=R+1}^M f_i}; \\ y &= \frac{y_l + y_r}{2} \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

These algorithms are utilized to design T2FCs in UAV.

6. SIMULATIONS

Six T2FC controllers are designed to implement the UAV control structure. The core of each T2FC is a type-2 fuzzy rule base that contains the input-output relationships. These relationships are expressed using type-2 fuzzy IF-Then rules, as presented in Table 1. Seven linguistic terms are used to describe both input and output variables. Using these linguistic values, the rules are constructed. The complete rule base consists of 49 type-2 "If-Then" rules. In Table 1, the linguistic values are denoted as follows: NL- negative large, PL- positive large, NM- negative medium, PM- positive medium, NS- negative small, PS- positive small, and Z-zero. Triangular type-2 MFs are used to express all linguistic values. The type-2 MFs for the input signals are shown in Fig. 4 (a,b). Fig. 5 depicts type-2 MFs of the output control signal.

The controller consists of five main components: a type-2 rule base, type-reduction, fuzzification, defuzzification and inference engine blocks. In this study, type-2 reduction is performed in conjunction with the defuzzification algorithm to compute the crisp values. The T2FCs are developed to control the UAV's z, x, and y positions, as well as yaw- ψ , roll- ϕ and pitch- θ angles. Accordingly, the UAV control system employs a total of six T2FC controllers.

Table 1. Rule base

		Change_in_Error (e_{i+1})						
		NL	NM	NS	Z	PS	PM	PL
Error (e)	NL	PL	PL	PL	PL	PM	PS	Z
	NM	PL	PL	PL	PM	PS	Z	NS
	NS	PL	PL	PM	PS	Z	NS	NM
	Z	PL	PM	PS	Z	NS	NM	NL
	PS	PM	PS	Z	NS	NM	NL	NL
	PM	PS	Z	NS	NM	NL	NL	NL
	PL	Z	NS	NM	NL	NL	NL	NL

Fig.4. MFs: (a) Error, (b) Change-in-error

Fig.5. MFs of the control signal

We simulated the proposed T2FCS (see Fig.2) using a Matlab program. The dynamic equations presented in Sections 3 and 4 were employed for modelling the system. For the simulation, the following plant parameters were used [9,34]: Drag coefficient $d=1.1 \cdot 10^{-6}$, Thrust coefficient $b=3.13 \cdot 10^{-5}$, Half-length $l=0.17$ m, Mass $m=0.38$ kg, Moments of inertia on x, y and z axes are $I_x=0.0086$ kg.m², $I_y=0.0086$ kg.m² and

$I_z=0.0172$ kg.m², correspondingly. Moment of inertia of rotor $J_{tp} = 0.00006$ kg.m².

The designed T2FCs are employed to control z, x, y positions, as well as yaw- ψ , roll- ϕ and pitch- θ angles. Stepwise reference signals $G=(z,x,y,\phi, \theta,\psi)$ are applied for testing the control system. The initial values for positions and angles are set to $G=(0,0,0,0,0,0)$. Here roll and pitch variables are intermediate variables used to regulate x and y positions. We changed the reference signals every 10 seconds (1000 steps) as (5, 5, 5, $\phi, \theta, 0.3$), (10, 10, 10, $\phi, \theta, 0.5$), (5, 5, 5, $\phi, \theta, 0.3$), then (10, 10, 10, $\phi, \theta, 0.5$). As previously mentioned, different reference signals were applied to the control system. Theoretically, pitch and roll angles should remain negligibly small. The desired values of θ and ϕ angles are determined using (18) and (19). By controlling these angles, the x and y positions of a UAV are regulated. The control system performance for each channel is assessed using the root mean square error (RMSE).

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (y_i^d - y_i)^2}{N}} \quad (26)$$

Here, y_i and y_i^d are the current and desired output signals of the plant, N is the number of iterations.

The results of simulations are shown in Figs.6-9. Fig. 6(a,b,c,d) illustrates the plots of time-response characteristic of z, x and y positions and yaw angle using the type-2 fuzzy control system. Here, solid lines are plots of current, and dotted lines are plots of desired signals. As shown from the transient characteristics, the settling times for x, y and z positions and yaw angle are between 3 and 3.5 seconds. Statistical errors are equal to zero, and no overshoot occurs. Fig. 7(a,b) presents the plots of the response characteristics of roll (ϕ) and pitch (θ) angles.

Fig. 8(a,b,c,d) presents the error plots obtained for (a) z , (b) x and (c) y positions and (d) the yaw ψ angle. As shown in the figures, when the control signals of the T2FC controller are changed suddenly in a short time interval, the x, y, z coordinates and ψ angle are also changed suddenly. After the stabilization of the positions, the control signals are stabilized and become equal to their previous values. Fig. 9(a, b) presents the plots of the errors for (a) roll ϕ and (b) pitch θ angles. Using the response characteristics of the variables, the RMSE is used to evaluate control systems performance. Table 2 depicts the RMSE values of the control systems for regulating x, y, z positions and the ψ angle. The results of T2FC based control system are compared with the results of the PID control systems. Comparative results confirm the superior performance of the T2FC-based control system (Table 2).

In the next experiment, the T2FC-based control system of the UAV was simulated using the desired reference signals from [50]. In this case, the trajectory tracking of the UAV is evaluated. Desired signals for x, y and z positions are changed as

$$\begin{aligned} X_{des}(t) &= 2\sin(0.5t); & Y_{des}(t) &= 2\cos(0.5t); \\ Z_{des}(t) &= 1; & \psi_{des}(t) &= 0; \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

Fig.6. Response characteristics: (a) z -axis, (b) x - axis, (c) y- axis, (d) Yaw angle.

Table 2. Performance characteristics

Controllers' performances		PID	T2FC
X position	SSE	3.5852	2.0031
	RMSE	1.8935	1.4153
Y position	SSE	3.5721	2.0540
	RMSE	1.890	1.4332
Z position	SSE	0.1755	0.9684
	RMSE	0.4190	0.9841
ψ Yaw angle	SSE	0.0004	0.0023
	RMSE	0.0197	0.0480

Fig.7. Response characteristics: (a) Roll angle, (b) Pitch angle.

Fig.8. Plots of the control signals: (a) z -axis, (b) x - axis, (c) y- axis, (d) Yaw angle.

Fig.9. Plots of the control signals: (a) Roll angle, (b) Pitch angle.

We ran the control system (see Fig.2) and obtained the response characteristics of the control variables. Fig. 10 depicts the positions of the UAV in 3D space. The response characteristics obtained from the simulations are presented in Fig. 11 and Fig. 12. Here, dotted lines depict the desired signals and solid lines denote the current signals. Fig. 11(a,b,c) depicts the response characteristics of the positions z , x and y , respectively. In the figures, the solid line depicts the current signal, and the dotted line is the desired signal. As shown, the dynamics of the x and y positions changed sinusoidally. Fig. 12(a,b) depicts the plots of pitch and roll angles. The response characteristics of the pitch and roll angles are also changed sinusoidally.

The results obtained for the T2FCS are compared with the results of the PID control systems using the desired signals (26). Table 3 depicts the SSE and RMSE values of positions obtained during simulations using T2FC and PID controllers. As shown, the T2FCS achieves better performance in controlling x and y positions than the PID control system.

Table 3. Performance characteristics

Controllers' performances		PID	T2FC
X position	SSE	0.2075	0.0020
	RMSE	0.4556	0.0448
Y position	SSE	0.3029	0.1051
	RMSE	0.5504	0.3242
Z position	SSE	0.001	0.0012
	RMSE	0.032	0.0345

In the third simulation, the following desired signals are used for testing the trajectory tracking of the T2FC system of the UAV [11]

$$\begin{aligned}
 X_{des}(t) &= 0.5\cos(0.5t); & Y_{des}(t) &= 0.5\sin(0.5t); \\
 Z_{des}(t) &= 2+0.1t; & \psi_{des}(t) &= 60^\circ;
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{28}$$

Fig.10. Plot of the UAV in 3D space

Fig. 11. Plots of controlled variables: (a) z - axis, (b) x - axis, (c) y - axis.

Fig. 12. Plots of controlled variables: (a) Roll angle, (b) Pitch angle

Fig.13. Plot of the UAV in 3D space

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Fig. 14. Plots of controlled variables: (a) Z -axis, (b) X -axis, (c) Y- axis, (d) Roll angle.

The trajectory tracking results of the UAV is shown in Fig.13 in 3D space. Fig.14(a,b,c,d) and Fig. 15(a,b) depict the response characteristics. In the figures, the solid lines depict the current signals and the dotted lines depict the desired signal. The results indicate that the T2FC control system enables more accurate tracking of the reference trajectories, even when the initial positions are far from the desired signals. As shown, the current z , x and y positions and ψ yaw angle of the UAV follow the

reference signals in a short time, and as a result, the transient characteristics of the control system become smooth.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 15. Plots of controlled variables: (a) Pitch angle, (b) Yaw angle

Analysis of Results. The simulation results obtained indicate that the T2FCS is more effective than classical control systems for UAV control and trajectory tracking. As shown in Fig.6 and Table 2, the T2FC-based system can effectively stabilize the attitude and altitude of the UAV better than the PD control system. As shown in Fig. 6(a), the T2FCS can drive the z position from zero to 10m and stabilize the position in 3 seconds with zero static error. Also, x and y positions and ψ yaw angle can be driven to the desired value from the zero and stabilized in 3.5 seconds (Fig.6(b,c,d)). During stabilization, the static errors obtained for the controlled variables are equal to zero. For all variables, the maximum overshoot was calculated to be zero. The values of RMSE for x , y , z positions and yaw angle of the T2FC-based control system were 1.41, 1.43, 0.9684 and 0.048, respectively.

In trajectory tracking, the desired signals of the x and y positions were represented by sinusoidal signals. z was taken as equal to 1. Fig. 11(a,b,c) shows that the x position is stabilised in a very short time of 1 second, the y position is stabilised in 3 seconds, and the z position in 4 seconds. Static errors for all variables are equal to zero. The RMSE values for x , y and z positions were calculated as 0.0448, 0.3242 and 0.0345, respectively.

In the second trajectory tracking problem (28), the x position was stabilised in 3 seconds, the y position in 0.1 seconds, and the z position and the yaw (ψ) angle were stabilised in 3 seconds. The static errors for all parameters were zero.

7. CONCLUSIONS

A T2FC-based control system for the UAV is proposed in this study. The kinematics and dynamical models of the UAV are first explained, and a two-level control structure based on T2FC is then designed. The proposed

T2FC is employed to control x -, y - and z positions, as well as roll, pitch and yaw, angles of the UAV. The type-2 rule base of the controller and its inference algorithm are presented. Using an α -level procedure and inreval type-2 fuzzy logic, the design principle of the T2FC is described. The T2FC-based control system was modelled to evaluate its performance and to demonstrate the suitability of the proposed approach. Comparisons between the T2FC- and PID-based control systems were conducted, and the results proved the effectiveness of the T2FC. In particular, the RMSE values of the transient response characteristics were reduced. The proposed type-2 fuzzy controllers were also tested on a real UAV constructed in our research laboratory, yielding satisfactory results. Overall, the comparative analysis indicated the effectiveness of the type-2 fuzzy control system.

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